

APPLICATION OF THE DIBR II - TOPSIS HYBRID MODEL IN THE SELECTION OF A FORM OF MANOEUVRE IN URBAN OFFENSIVE OPERATIONS

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Abstract

Modern military operations are characterized by high dynamism and uncertainty, demanding rapid decision-making that accounts for numerous complex factors. Urban offensive operations, in particular, present unique challenges due to dense terrain, the presence of civilians, and the fluid nature of combat dynamics. Selecting the optimal form of maneuver is a critical component in developing a course of action (COA) and requires the balancing of multiple, often conflicting, criteria. This paper presents a hybrid multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) model that integrates the DIBR II (Defining Interrelationships Between Ranked Criteria II) and TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution) methods to support informed and structured decision-making at the tactical level. DIBR II is used to determine the relative importance of criteria, while TOPSIS identifies the most suitable form of maneuver based on proximity to an ideal solution. The model is applied to a simulated urban operation scenario, evaluating maneuver forms against expert-defined criteria. This approach reduces subjectivity and enhances decision efficiency by providing a transparent and replicable framework. Universal criteria for maneuver selection, as proposed by military experts, are incorporated. Beyond maneuver selection, the model demonstrates potential applicability to other aspects of operational planning, such as risk assessment and target prioritization.

Keywords: urban offensive operations, DIBR II, TOPSIS, form of manoeuvre, military decision-making

Introduction

In modern military operations, time is a critical resource, and therefore, planning operations must be carried out efficiently with optimal time management. The urban environment is specific and

demanding in terms of planning, organizing, and executing combat operations, and it is often necessary to analyze a large number of diverse factors. Consequently, commanders and staff must rapidly eliminate infeasible options and focus resources on developing those courses of action (COAs) that offer the highest probability of success. In certain phases of this process, multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) methods can be applied as a decision-support tool.

In this paper, the DIBR II (Defining Interrelationships Between Ranked Criteria II) – TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution) model was applied to identify the most optimal form of maneuver concerning the selected criteria, so that they could be used in the further planning process for course of action (COA) modeling. The development of COA, which is essentially based on the scheme of maneuver, is a crucial phase in the operational planning process, initiated by output products created during the orientation phase (General Staff of the Serbian Armed Forces, 2017). The form of maneuver refers to the specific tactical approach selected to defeat the enemy. It is one aspect of the broader scheme of maneuver (Department of the Army, 2024a). The scheme of maneuver is the overarching plan that dictates how the mission will be executed, while the form of maneuver is a specific tactic chosen to effectively engage the enemy within that plan.

In the doctrinal documents of the armed forces of most countries, there is generally agreement regarding the definition and classification of maneuver forms. In Army Doctrine Publication (ADP) 3-90 – *Offense and Defense* (2019), the form of the maneuver is defined as “distinct tactical combinations of fire and movement with a unique set of doctrinal characteristics that differ primarily in the relationship between the maneuvering force and the enemy”. Essentially, it describes the initial deployment of combat forces (infantry, mechanized, and armored units), the role of each element, and their movement and actions concerning the objects of action. In principle, one form of maneuver is usually selected in an offensive operation, and a COA is further developed based on it (Department of the Army, 2023). This may ultimately involve a combination of several forms of maneuver, especially at a higher tactical level, where one is dominant during execution and can be changed at various stages of an operation, typically managed by regrouping forces along defined phase lines (Slavković et al., 2018). This is particularly evident in assault operations in urban areas, given the strong influence of the urban environment across all dimensions of the operation.

It is important to emphasize that the selected form significantly influences the scheme of maneuver, which is a key part of the COA development in the planning process. It is crucial to highlight that applying the aforementioned model should not in any way exclude the creativity and experience of specialist officers.

This paper presents several scientific contributions. It introduces, for the first time, the application of the DIBR II–TOPSIS model for selecting form of maneuver within tactical-level operational planning, with a focus on COA development in urban offensive operations. The study demonstrates the practical value of hybrid MCDM models in reducing subjectivity and enhancing transparency and consistency when evaluating tactical criteria. Furthermore, it extends the scope of MCDM applications beyond the commonly addressed areas of equipment selection and site evaluation, positioning these methods within the domain of tactical planning in complex operational environments. Finally, the paper proposes a structured approach for integrating the model into existing doctrinal planning frameworks. The proposed model utilizes two methods to minimize subjectivity in evaluating and ranking criteria and selecting alternatives. The DIBR II method is employed to assess

and determine the weight coefficients of the criteria, while the TOPSIS method facilitates the ranking of the considered maneuver forms.

The literature analysis leads to the conclusion that MCDM methods have been applied in many areas of military activities, individually or in combination of two or more methods (hybrid models) in order to most appropriately utilize their capabilities in supporting the finding of an optimal solution to the problem.

Hybrid MCDM models that integrate DIBR II and TOPSIS methods with other methods have already been applied to solve a wide variety of problems: the DIBR II-rough MABAC model for ranking management methods and techniques in the technical maintenance process (Božanić et al., 2024); DIBR-TOPSIS model for the selection of infantry landing sites when crossing a river with an aluminum M70 boat (Žnidaršič et al., 2024); the DIBR II-BM-CoCoSo model for supporting the selection of an assault boat (Tešić et al., 2023a); the Fuzzy DIBR-Fuzzy DIBR II-EWAA-BM-DEXi-Fuzzy LMAW model for selecting a water obstacle crossing point in a defensive operation (Tešić et al., 2024); the DIBR II-NWBM-FF MAIRCA model for selecting a pontoon bridge (Tešić et al., 2023b); Pamučar et al. (2016) apply the Fuzzy AHP-TOPSIS model in the selection of a brigade artillery group's firing position in a defensive operation; Hamurcu and Eren (2020) apply the TOPSIS method to select an unmanned aerial vehicle; Ardil (2022) applies the TOPSIS method to select a fighter aircraft, while Qu S. et al. (2021) apply the same method to assess the effectiveness of an early warning system against missile threats; Esfandiari and Rizvandi (2014) apply the TOPSIS method to rank different models for strategic planning; Yıldızbaşı and Gür (2020) apply the AHP-TOPSIS model to select the use of unmanned aerial vehicles in decision-making support during natural disasters; Tesić et al. (2025) developed an MCDM model for selecting network planning techniques in the military during the execution of engineering tasks related to overcoming water obstacles; Radovanović et al. (2024) introduced a hybrid LMAW-G-EDAS model for selecting an assault rifle for military purposes, showing how well-defined criteria and appropriate mathematical models can improve the procurement and selection process. A similar topic is explored in their earlier work (Radovanović et al., 2023), where an MCDM approach was applied to the selection of an automatic rifle, emphasizing the importance of methodological consistency and transparency in decisions affecting combat effectiveness; Pamučar, Božanić, and Đorović (2011) analyzed the use of fuzzy logic in the decision-making process within the Armed Forces of the Republic of Serbia. Their work is among the pioneering studies in the region that apply non-classical decision-making methods in military systems.

The analysis of the literature reveals that hybrid MCDM models, particularly those integrating DIBR II and TOPSIS, have proven effective in a wide array of military applications, including military equipment selection, logistics and engineering operations, tactical planning, and strategic assessment. However, despite this broad applicability, no prior research has addressed the use of MCDM methods to support the selection of maneuver forms during the operational planning process at the tactical level. This study addresses that gap by proposing a hybrid DIBR II-TOPSIS model for optimizing the selection of maneuver forms as a foundation for more effective COA modeling, particularly in complex environments such as urban operations.

The paper is structured in several parts. Following the introduction, which briefly explains the importance of selecting the optimal maneuver form when modeling a COA, the second part outlines

the steps of the DIBR II and TOPSIS methods. The following describes the alternatives and criteria, and then presents the results obtained by applying the proposed model.

Description of the DIBR II method

The DIBR II method was developed by Božanić and Pamučar (2023). This method belongs to the group of subjective methods for determining the weighting coefficient of criteria. It was introduced in 2023, through several scientific papers (Božanić & Pamučar, 2023; Tešić et al., 2023a; 2023b), and was created by improving upon the earlier DIBR method. This method is implemented through nine steps, which are described below.

Step 1. In this step, a set of criteria (S) is defined that will be used to rank the alternatives $S = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n\}$. These criteria can be quantitative or qualitative, depending on the specific problem.

Step 2. In this step, the criteria are ranked from the most important (C_1) to the least important (C_n), which can be represented by the expression: $C_1 > C_2 > C_3 \dots > C_n$.

Step 3. This step has two substeps. In the first substep, the significance relationships between adjacent criteria are determined, using the following expressions:

$$\frac{w_1}{w_2} = \frac{d_{1,2}}{1} \rightarrow \frac{w_1}{w_2} = d_{1,2} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{w_2}{w_3} = \frac{d_{2,3}}{1} \rightarrow \frac{w_2}{w_3} = d_{2,3} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{w_{n-1}}{w_n} = \frac{d_{n-1,n}}{1} \rightarrow \frac{w_{n-1}}{w_n} = d_{n-1,n} \quad (3)$$

where $d_{1,2}, d_{2,3}, \dots, d_{n-1,n}$ represent the value of the importance ratio of adjacent criteria.

In the second substep, the significance ratio between the most significant and least significant criteria is defined, which plays the role of a control factor when assessing the quality of significance of neighboring criteria.

$$\frac{w_1}{w_n} = \frac{d_{1,n}}{1} \rightarrow \frac{w_1}{w_n} = d_{1,n} \quad (4)$$

Step 4. Based on expressions (1), (2), and (3), this step displays the second and other lower-ranked criteria over the most important criterion:

$$w_2 = \frac{w_1}{d_{1,2}} \quad (5)$$

$$w_3 = \frac{w_2}{d_{2,3}} = \frac{w_1}{d_{1,2} \times d_{2,3}} \quad (6)$$

...

$$w_n = \frac{w_1}{d_{1,2} \times d_{2,3} \times \dots \times d_{n-1,n}} \quad (7)$$

Step 5. Calculation of the value of the most significant criterion. By applying expressions (5) to (7), we obtain the formula for calculating the value of the most significant criterion, and by entering the significance values of the neighboring criteria ($d_{1,2}, d_{2,3}, \dots, d_{n-1,n}$):

$$w_1 = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{d_{1,2}} + \frac{1}{d_{1,2} \times d_{2,3}} + \dots + \frac{1}{d_{1,2} \times d_{2,3} \times \dots \times d_{n-1,n}}} \quad (8)$$

Step 6. Calculation of weighting coefficients of other criteria. By applying formulas (5) to (7), the weighting coefficients of other criteria, w_2, w_3, \dots, w_n , are calculated.

Step 7. This is the last step of the method, and it is checked in order to eliminate subjectivity in decision-making as much as possible. Quality assessment of defined significance is carried out based on the significance ratio of the most significant and least significant criteria.

$$w_n^c = \frac{w_1}{d_{1,n}} \quad (9)$$

where w_n^c represents the control weight coefficient of criterion C_n .

The values of the weight coefficient of the least significant criterion w_n , and w_n^c should be approximately equal. If the deviation is up to 10%, it can be concluded that the significance ratio is defined correctly. The deviation is checked by applying the formula:

$$d_n = \left| 1 - \frac{w_n}{w_n^c} \right| \quad (10)$$

where d_n represents the deviation value of the weight coefficient of the criterion C_n .

To ensure the validity of the comparison, the condition $0 \leq d_n \leq 0.1$ must be met. If $d_n > 0.1$, then it is necessary to define the relationships between the criteria in a different way.

Description of the TOPSIS method

The TOPSIS method is a multi-criteria decision-making method developed by Hwang and Yoon (1982). This method is based on determining the distance of the optimal solution from the ideal solution (the best possible solution) and the negative ideal solution (the worst possible solution). The optimal solution should be as close to the ideal as possible, or as far away from the negative ideal solution as possible (Chen & Hwang, 1992). The method consists of 6 steps, and it is easy to implement.

Considering that the TOPSIS method is already well described in a large number of scientific papers, the steps of the method will not be described here.

Description of the alternatives and the criteria

This part of the paper describes five forms of maneuver that will be ranked using the model previously described in order to select the optimal alternative: frontal attack, infiltration, penetration, turning movement, and envelopment.

Frontal attack (A1)

The frontal attack is a direct assault conducted against the enemy's forward defensive positions. Its use should be limited to situations where friendly forces possess significant combat overmatch or when the operational environment provides favorable conditions for its execution (Department of the Army, 2022b).

Infiltration (A2)

Infiltration is a form of maneuver employed to move combat elements covertly through or around enemy positions to achieve positional advantage without triggering decisive engagement. In urban operations, infiltration is used to seize key terrain, disrupt command and control nodes, or establish lodgments in depth, typically along the enemy's flanks or rear. Effective execution requires detailed reconnaissance, decentralized execution, and disciplined small-unit actions to exploit gaps in the enemy's disposition (Department of the Army, 2022b; 2024b).

Penetration (A3)

Penetration is a deliberate form of maneuver that concentrates combat power along a narrow front to rupture enemy defensive lines and create conditions for exploitation. In urban operations, this maneuver is employed to breach fortified positions, establish a foothold, and facilitate the destruction or dislocation of enemy forces in depth. Successful penetration demands detailed intelligence preparation of the urban environment, robust breaching capabilities, and the timely commitment of follow-on forces to consolidate gains and secure exposed flanks (Department of the Army, 2022b; 2024b).

Turning movement (A4)

The turning movement is a doctrinal form of maneuver that seeks to avoid the strength of enemy defenses by dislocating the enemy through the seizure of key terrain and infrastructure in the rear or on the flanks, thereby rendering enemy positions untenable. In urban operations, this maneuver is particularly effective for achieving objectives with minimal collateral damage, as it compels the enemy to reposition or retreat without necessitating high-intensity direct engagements within densely populated areas (Department of the Army, 2022a; 2022b).

Envelopment (A5)

Envelopment is a maneuver that aims to attack the enemy's flanks or rear to isolate and destroy forces by circumventing their main defenses. In the urban operational environment, envelopment can be executed through various spatial dimensions: horizontally, vertically (via airborne or air assault operations), or subterranean routes (Department of the Army, 2024b).

It is important to note that there is no single set of criteria for selecting the form of maneuver, but the command and staff have the flexibility to create them based on the specifics of the mission and type of operation. In practice, the most common criteria include elements of combat functions (command and control, movement and maneuver, fire, intelligence activities, force protection, sustainability), principles specific to the type of operation according to the doctrine of a particular armed force (e.g., surprise, tempo, coordination, etc.), actions and counteractions, risk, as well as other elements that are significant for the execution of the mission.

The complexity and specificity of the research problem necessitated the involvement of military experts to define the criteria. Eight criteria were established for selecting the most optimal form of maneuver (Table 1).

Table 1. Description of the criteria.

Criterion	Description	Type of criterion
Relative force ratio (C1)	Relative force ratio refers to the comparison of friendly and enemy combat power in both numerical and qualitative terms. In urban operations, where dense terrain favors the defender and complicates maneuver, significantly higher force ratios are required. Doctrine recommends ratios from 3:1 up to 15:1, based on mission type and threat level (Department of the Army, 2022a; 2024b).	<i>benefit</i>
Urban terrain suitability (C2)	Urban terrain suitability assesses the compatibility of the built environment, such as structural density, street patterns, vertical and subterranean features, with specific forms of maneuver. Dense urban areas constrain vehicular mobility, disrupt unit cohesion, and degrade command and control systems (Department of the Army, 2022a; 2024b).	<i>benefit</i>
Enemy disposition and defence posture (C3)	This factor refers to the enemy's force composition, deployment, and defensive readiness within the urban area. Densely concentrated or well-prepared defenses often necessitate penetration to breach fortified positions. In contrast, dispersed, uncoordinated, or poorly integrated defenses may be more effectively engaged through infiltration, or envelopment, exploiting gaps in the enemy's posture (Department of the Army, 2024b).	<i>cost</i>
Risk to friendly forces (C4)	This factor assesses how likely friendly forces are to suffer casualties or experience combat power loss when executing a specific maneuver form. If preserving forces remains a top priority, military planners choose safer tactics like infiltration or envelopment. Commanders need to weigh operational goals with acceptable risk levels to guarantee mission success while preventing excessive losses (Department of the Army, 2022a; 2024b).	<i>cost</i>
Mission objective (C5)	This criterion considers the desired operational end state, such as terrain seizure, enemy destruction, area isolation, or personnel recovery. The selected form of maneuver should align with the objective to maximize effectiveness and probability of success (Department of the Army, 2024a).	<i>benefit</i>
Potential for surprise (C6)	This factor evaluates the probability of executing tactical surprise, which will reduce enemy response capabilities. Achieving surprise can disrupt enemy decision-making processes, degrade morale, and generate significant psychological shock, providing a decisive advantage in urban operations. As the potential for surprise grows stronger, it directly enhances operational freedom, which leads to mission success.	<i>benefit</i>
Resource requirements (C7)	Amount and type of resources needed to execute the maneuver. Complex or resource-intensive maneuvers (e.g., vertical envelopment) may be constrained by availability; simpler options may be more feasible in resource-limited scenarios. Lower resource use is more sustainable and efficient.	<i>cost</i>
Civilian impact (C8)	This criterion evaluates the potential for collateral damage and civilian disruption resulting from the chosen form of maneuver. Minimizing civilian impact is essential for maintaining legitimacy and long-term mission success.	<i>cost</i>

Results of the model application

This part of the paper presents a multi-criteria decision analysis using the TOPSIS method to evaluate five alternatives. In the first step, after defining the criteria (Table 1), the experts ranked the criteria based on their assessment of their impact on offensive operations in an urban environment, as follows: $C4 > C5 > C2 > C6 > C1 = C3 > C7 > C8$.

By applying the formulas given in Steps 3 to 6, the significance ratio between adjacent criteria was determined, and then the coefficient values of the most important and other criteria were calculated (Table 2).

Table 2. Weighting coefficients of criteria obtained by applying the DIBR II method.

	<i>C1</i>	<i>C2</i>	<i>C3</i>	<i>C4</i>	<i>C5</i>	<i>C6</i>	<i>C7</i>	<i>C8</i>
<i>w</i>	0.101	0.139	0.101	0.192	0.174	0.127	0.088	0.077

Risk to friendly forces (*C4*) is weighted highest (0.192) due to doctrinal emphasis on force protection in urban operations. The lowest criterion value was assigned to *C8*.

The calculation determined that the deviation ($d_3 = 0.000141$) is within the limits of permissible values (less than 10%).

In the subsequent procedure, the TOPSIS method was applied. Since all the criteria described in Table 1 are linguistic, a translation scale was established to create a normalized decision matrix, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Linguistic rating scale.

Linguistic term	Numerical value
Extremely Poor	1
Very Poor	2
Poor	3
Below Average	4
Average	5
Above Average	6
Good	7
Very Good	8
Excellent	9

Military experts - members of the staff, based on a fictive scenario, assessed the adequacy of the offered forms of maneuvers to the defined criteria, using the terms given in Table 4.

Table 4. Initial decision matrix.

	<i>C1</i>	<i>C2</i>	<i>C3</i>	<i>C4</i>	<i>C5</i>	<i>C6</i>	<i>C7</i>	<i>C8</i>
A1	9	6	5	7	8	3	5	3
A2	6	7	5	4	7	8	6	8
A3	8	8	8	6	9	5	7	5
A4	7	9	7	5	8	7	6	6
A5	8	7	7	5	8	6	7	5
Criteria character	max	max	min	min	max	max	min	min

By applying mathematical formulas, the final results were obtained, which are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Final ranking of alternatives.

	<i>Si+</i>	<i>Si-</i>	<i>C_i[*]</i>	Rank
A1	0.0715	0.0439	0.3805	5
A2	0.0440	0.0703	0.6150	2
A3	0.0511	0.0415	0.4481	4
A4	0.0337	0.0581	0.6332	1
A5	0.0388	0.0496	0.5611	3

The most optimal form of maneuver is Turning Movement (A4), because it has the highest value of relative proximity to the ideal solution (C_i^*). The analysis identifies Turning Movement (A4) as the most suitable maneuver alternative within the given scenario. Both Envelopment (A5) and Infiltration (A2) are very close in performance. Penetration (A3) achieved a moderate standing due to its elevated logistical burden and force protection requirements. Frontal Attack (A1) ranked lowest, as its inherent high-risk profile and limited tactical surprise.

Conclusion

In complex combat conditions, each element of the operation must be carefully analyzed and planned in order to achieve optimal results. Traditional planning methods often fail to adequately respond to all the challenges of modern armed conflicts, which emphasizes the need to introduce new methods and techniques.

The conclusion of this paper highlights key elements for improving the operations planning process, with a particular emphasis on the application of MCDM methods. Specifically, the hybrid model combining DIBR II and TOPSIS methods offers a practical tool for supporting the military decision-making process, especially in steps such as COA modeling. This paper presents the first application of the DIBR II–TOPSIS model for selecting the most optimal form of maneuver. The DIBR II method provides a more objective approach to determining the weighting of evaluation criteria, thereby reducing the subjectivity inherent in traditional methods. Moreover, its simplicity makes it accessible and easy to use for military experts involved in the decision-making process. Complementing this, the TOPSIS method facilitates the selection of the most suitable maneuver by considering multiple performance criteria, thus enhancing the overall efficiency and reliability of decisions. Also, this method allows the simultaneous consideration of a large number of factors that can affect the performance of an operation.

The criteria for selecting the form of force maneuver that are defined in this paper can contribute to making more objective decisions. Furthermore, this paper can represent the basis for further research in the field of applying various models of multi-criteria optimization in planning military operations in specific conditions, which would be very important considering that there are almost no scientific papers in which MCDM methods have been applied in the field of infantry unit tactics.

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